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Application of work and time study in production systems to improve productivity and effectiveness

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Abstract. This paper describes and emphasizes the importance of work and time study, time standards, additionally, contains a practical case study of their application area. Any facility can be developed by the usage of time study techniques and right application of work evaluation methodologies. Managers always try to minimize the production time almost in every production facility as possible as they can. The development can be achieved on more efficient raw material usage, saving energy, high utilization of machinery, time reduction, high productivity, higher profit and etc. The study case contains many applications of production improvement and time and cost reduction techniques, like one-piece flow, simultaneous production, machine, method optimization and etc. The selection process of correct machinery is too important that by this the production can be optimized in a huge amount differently from small-step improvements. The profits and effects of these methods are different from each other, that depend on characteristics of the production and its market requirements and especially quality demands. The elimination of ineffective processes gives big chances to the producers to focus on all quality factors and by this almost all of production time is spent for the real target of the producer.

Keywords: *time study, work evaluation, one-piece flow, simultaneous production, machine optimization.*

Introduction

In the modern world the production facilities have different characteristics depending on which kind of products are produced there. The difference caused by the assignment of the products (how frequently the customers need the products), the work power of the facility and the machinery, especially the usage and quality demands for the product.

To manage the differences and use them as advantage for the facility all facility activities must be investigated by work study. Work study consists of time, motion and method

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study and work evaluation. Luchien Karsten indicated the importance of work study, especially time and motion study [13]. The real power of any company is calculated by its productivity power. Murshida Khatun has broadly investigated the effects of time and motion study on productivity [3]. The research shows the importance of work study for every company. Pedro Henrique Araujo Cury, Jose Saraiva also investigated this influence [12]. The productivity of company depends on some factors like human force, machinery, production technology, quality demands and etc. International Labor Office's research indicates that even working time affects the productivity in big amount [7]. The productivity and performance of any company can be developed by standardizing time of all machinery and workers at the same time as possible as the company can do. Time standards are so essential in modern production industry. Abraham Y. Nahm, Mark A. Vonderembse, S. Subba Rao, T. S. Ragu-Nathan have investigated the importance of time calculations and its usage in a business environment [10].

Work evaluation is different from time and motion study. Because the work evaluation is sum of measurement and calculation activities to get the work efficiency and productivity. To optimize the performance of any company it is important to do appropriate time-based measurements and calculations. To measure the work correctly it is important to assign right measurement methodology and standards you will do calculations on it. Waldemar Karwowski, Mansour Rahimi researched about work measurement and gave some good examples for this in the paper [4]. After all calculations and measure the companies need to improve and develop the measured factors to get better efficiency. To achieve the development, it is so important to use collected data more correctly. The decisions gotten from the analysis of data collected are the main sources to get improvements. A. Sai Nishanth Reddy, P. Srinath Rao, Rajyalakshmi G. have indicated the importance of the analysis of the data [9]. Only after the analysis the company can develop its activities in time to get more profit and achieve low production time. Xenophon A. Koufteros, Mark A. Vonderembse, William J. Doll show some methods to improve the measures [2]. Even sometimes improving measurement methodology itself helps the company to get more effectiveness.

Content

As mentioned above in a work study the most important

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thing is to collect useful data. Data collection can be done by daily, weekly, monthly and etc. reports, observations, speaking with workers and managers, video records and etc. M. Forsman, G. A. Hansson, L. Medbo, P. Asterland, T. Engström indicated the importance of video recordings in work study and work analysis [6]. There are some technical methods that helps researcher to get more data based on the data collected. For example, if enough data you have on hand you can generate more data with them by the help of regression method. Regression equation is shown in nomenclature section. This method and the other methods help researchers to save time and get the result quickly. But anyway, the most part of work study analysis is spent to collect data. Because if the calculations are done wrongly and then suggest solutions based on this calculations and measures, every activity that done for work study can be accepted as waste. There are different measurement methods that researchers use to collect the data. Metin Dağdeviren, Ergün Eraslan, Fatih V. Çelebi show the importance of different measurement methods in a production company [1]. After the data collection process and its analysis every useful data can improve our production positively [8]. Motion study also important to develop productivity. Because if the material flow within the production company is not organized effectively, it is impossible to get the efficiency and productivity with time standards. The method study is also important on the way that takes the company to success. The production methods and technology are not only important for a production company, it can be said that it is vital. Because all the useless activities take time in a production and the time itself means money and the biggest sign of competitiveness. Saving time can be achieved by the all activities fulfilled to decrease the production time. Production scheduling and balancing are the desired results of work study, especially method study. Haresh Gurnani, Pravin K. Johri indicates the importance of scheduling [5]. Reducing delays in production is the one of the main objectives of production companies. It is possible to reduce the production time with operations research methods too. The delays, and time can be eliminated as possible as we can by minimization with different optimization programs. This is also a big step goes to high productivity [11]. Repetitive work sometimes causes delays itself. This kind of work also creates health problems on workers. Observations and other method study techniques can solve the problem

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completely. B. Juul-Kristensen, N. Fallentin, C. Ekdahl emphasizes the problem, too [14]. It is a fact that if a work is repeated continuously, it is so easy to simplify it or automate it that will help the companies to get the better productivity.

It is written above about work evaluation above that is important to collect useful data. The other advantage of work evaluation is to create wage system. Work evaluation helps companies assign correct workers to specific works. By correct wage systems the companies ensure that they pay workers in the amount they get from the workers. Wage systems are essential to encourage and motivate workers.

Assigning time standards

To find time standards normal time must be found for the processes. Normal time calculation depends on the pace of work. The normal time is calculated with this equation:

$$\text{Average time} * \text{Pace of work} = \text{Normal time}$$

The pace of work values must be assigned by engineers and technicians. The correct calculation depends on these calculations. Standard time is calculated by considering correct work speed percentage for the process. The percentage itself depends on the characteristics of work. The equation of standard time is like this:

$$\text{Normal time} * (1 + \text{percentage}) = \text{Standard time}$$

The calculation below shows how the data must be analyzed. The table shows the given time calculations in 4 period:

Table 1

Time record of making pastry process

Production process							
Process Code	Period	1	2	3	4	Ave	Amp
P1	Manual loading	145	200	158	147	163	55
P2	Automatic addition	48	45	44	46	46	4
P3	I operation	700	700	700	700	700	0
P4	Manual addition	34	13	25	19	23	21
P5	Automatic addition	76	74	78	78	77	4
P6	II operation	200	200	200	200	200	0
P7	Manual addition	32	130*	38	48	39	16
P8	Automatic addition	233	206	210	222	218	27
P9	III operation	700	700	700	700	700	0

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Table continuation 1

P10	Manual addition	75*	42	35	38	38	7
P11	Completing III operation	804	807	804	754	792	53
P12	Unloading	260	311	273	296	285	51
P13	Sending to next station	340*	52	28	29	36	24
Total						3317	

* - these values are not normal values. The value is so different from the following average value. Just for this reason these values are ignored in average time calculations.

Additionally, we need to calculate amplitude value for every measurement. The amplitude means the difference between the highest value and the smallest value in each measurement row. After the amplitude calculation we need to calculate the ratio of amplitude to average time for the process. These values show that to which process must be focused more than others. If the value is high this means the process has more problems that must be eliminated and developed. The table below shows this calculation:

Table 2

**Time record of making pastry process with amplitude
to average time ratio percentage**

Process Code	Ave	Amp	Amp/Ave %
P1	163	55	33.7 %
P2	46	4	8.7 %
P3	700	0	0.0 %
P4	23	21	91.3 %
P5	77	4	5.2 %
P6	200	0	0.0 %
P7	39	16	41.0 %
P8	218	27	12.4 %
P9	700	0	0.0 %
P10	38	7	18.4 %
P11	792	53	6.7 %
P12	285	51	17.9 %
P13	36	24	66.7 %
Total	3317		

In this calculation the processes with code P4 and P13 are the processes that must be improved firstly. Even the average time for the process is essential to start the investigation and corrections.

Other production activities can be improved by time study

To achieve the high level of productivity it is too important to organize the correct material flow within the

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production company. Only by providing one-piece flow system correctly companies can fulfil this target. A one-piece flow system itself demands perfect usage of current work power from production companies. Almost in all plants there are plenty of problems on organization of activities that the plants need to do to fulfil production as required. The problems can be solved easily by process simplification, simultaneous production activities and machine optimization (or optimization of work on machinery) and etc.

Conclusion

In the Summary it is clear that work study is so important to manage and improve all facility activities. Work study also considers ergonomic sides of production and material flow system. By considering the ergonomic conditions and time standards production engineers can easily organize the correct schedule of production activities and their machine route that the production processes must follow from raw material to ready product. After the scheduling the work force can be balanced on machinery and work stations to provide effective work division. The overall production activities must be optimized by work study techniques as motion, method and time study. Work study also contains work evaluation in it. Work evaluation and time study provides the production with main data that helps management and engineers to develop work activities and procedures. Differently motion and method study investigate ergonomic, technological, methodical, and possible feasibility and improvability sides of work. Finally, these techniques are the only choice if the target is developing the production facility.

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